

When it comes to predatory journals, is Scopus doing a good job after all?

A brief investigation

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Abstract

In an attempt to estimate the quality of an open access journal the indexing in the Scopus database is often perceived as a positive indicator. While the inclusion in the Beall's list is anticipated as at least a serious warning sign that the journal (or the publisher behind it) might be predatory. On numerous occasions it has been noticed that there are journals included in both lists/databases. This apparent discrepancy is recently investigated, and it was concluded that both lists are not flawless. This report investigated whether the journals included in the Beall's list are still in the list of Scopus titles or discontinued in the meantime.

Introduction

Publishing of peer reviewed research literature has been historically in the hands of publishers or stand-alone journals publishing conventional print-based academic journals according to the subscription-based publishing model. With the ever-extending possibilities of our computers and the world wide web a new publishing model is introduced, the open access model. Some even refer to it as an open access movement, with numerous 'idealistic' motivations like breaking the monopoly position of the big publishers and making scientific information available to everyone interested and all this for free [1-3]. If journals and publishers cannot charge the conventional subscription fees, they need to charge the authors (or the organizations behind them). A potential danger might be that those with less noble intentions will expect as many submitted

manuscripts as possible without proper peer review, since more published papers means more money. This potential danger and the seemingly unregulated growth of new journals and publishers led to worries about fake and fraudulent players in the academic publishing arena. Round 2010 a librarian called Jeffrey Beall started his crusade against what he called predatory journals, see for example [4]. Based on the above-described potential side-effects of the open access model, he focussed himself exclusively on open access Journals and Publishers. Since the introduction of his list "the Beall's list" has become more and more the 'holy bible' to determine on whether a journal or its publisher is predatory or not. No matter the semantic discussion on whether potential or possible leaves enough opening to a fair judgement of a particular journal or its publisher it is most of the times simply an indelible

conviction of that particular journal (or its publisher) and of the author(s) who published there. The Beall's list is basically used as to blacklist journals and publishers and is criticised as well [5-8]. Attempts are made to come up with whitelists as well [9] and one often used indicator is the Scopus index. In two recent papers quantified the number of journals included in the Beall's list that are indexed in Scopus as well [10, 11]. These recent papers triggered the here presented study.

Method

The paper with the disturbing title “Hundreds of 'predatory' journals indexed on leading scholarly database” [10] is based on the quantitative analysis of another paper [11]. This paper by Macháček & Srholec [11] is used in the here presented study. The supplement of the Macháček & Srholec paper [11] provides the full list of identified journals included in both the Beall's list and the Scopus list as found round 2017. In order to see whether these journals are still included in the Scopus list two lists were used: The list of Scopus included titles of October 2020 and the list of discontinued Scopus titles of February 2021.

Results

Overall view

The findings are summarized (see Table) and depicted in Figure 1. As described in the method section, the raw data that uses the supplement provided by Macháček & Srholec [11] and indicates whether the titles are still indexed in Scopus (this study) can be found in the supplement 1. As depicted in Figure 1 it is found that Scopus discontinued roughly 2/3 of all titles identified by Macháček & Srholec [11]. This can be interpreted in two different ways. Either Scopus is doing a good job by (eventually) identifying those titles that are

already been ‘judged’ by the Beall's list as not fulfilling the necessary quality requirements. Or it means that the Beall's list is wrong in 1/3 of all the Scopus indexed titles and wrongfully so identify them as potentially predatory.

Figure 1. In Green the journals now discontinued in Scopus and in Red those still indexed.

Frontiers

In this respect the Frontiers journals issue is an interesting case. All Frontiers journals (still active) are still included in the Scopus index, see also supplement 1. Macháček & Srholec [11] made some interesting remarks about Frontiers “The greatest controversy was triggered by inclusion of the Frontiers Research Foundation on Beall's list of publishers in October 2015. Beall defended this decision by pointing out several articles that, according to him, should not have been published. According to critics of this move, the Frontiers publisher is “legitimate and reputable and does offer proper peer-review” Most Frontiers journals are also indexed in the Web of Science and the Directory of Open Access Journals. Hence, judging by the relevance of Frontiers

Index	According to [11]	This study	No longer indexed
Indexed in Beall's list	323	321 ^a	2
Indexed in Scopus list	323	125	198
Indexed in Scopus without Frontiers Journals	290	94	196

^aThis refers to InTechOpen journals, for the sake of comparison this is not included in the calculation of percentages in Figure 1.

journals for the scientific community, there is a question mark about their inclusion on the predatory list.” This conclusion has been made before [8] and the fact that Scopus still includes their titles in their index seems to indicate that indeed the judgement made by Jeffrey Beall is wrong and this publisher should be delisted.

Specific cases

Frontiers in Bioscience (not related to the Frontiers journals) is still included in both lists. Inclusion in the Beall's list is questionable, since it is not only included in the Scopus index but is indexed in SCIE as well (2019 impact factor 2.747), see also: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Frontiers_in_Bioscience.

Scopus seems to disagree with the judgement made by the Beall's list when it comes to Bentham Open. All journals of Bentham Open are included in the Beall's list while Scopus still indexed 33 out of the (still) active 33 titles (it used to be 51 journals but Bentham Open discontinued a number of their journals themselves).

Conclusion

The use of the term predatory is discussed on numerous occasions. It is only since recently that it has been argued that first of all a definition is needed for the term predatory [12]. The Beall's list basically initiated its use. Regarding the limitations

of the Beall's list Macháček & Srholec [11] made some interesting remarks “In particular, caution is warranted when working with Beall's list of publishers. Classifying an entire publishing house as predatory is a strong judgment, and it cannot be ruled out that some journals which actually apply reputable standards have been blacklisted along the way. The list includes some publishers that maintain broad portfolios of dozens and even hundreds of journals, some of which may not deserve the predatory label, so that using Beall's list may result in overestimations of true “predators.” It is likely that the overwhelming majority of these journals are of poor quality, but poor quality is not a crime per se. One must, therefore, keep in mind that the list of publishers has been painted with a relatively broad brush.” This pretty much confirms the earlier conclusion that the Beall's list is not flawless [8]. The study presented here partly confirms these conclusions since Scopus disagree with the Beall's ‘verdict’ on quite a number of occasions (roughly in 1/3 of all cases) and keep the titles included in their index despite their inclusion in the Beall's list.

When it comes to Scopus Macháček & Srholec [11] conclude: “Last, but not least, there is the underlying question why there are predatory journals in Scopus in the first place. Journals indexed in Scopus should fulfil minimum quality requirements

(Scopus 2019). However, these criteria are either rather formal, derived from bibliometrics or rely on what the journal declares about itself. Predatory journals manage to look like regular scientific outlets on the outside, their bibliometric profile might not differ that much from other fringe journals and they do not shy away from lying about their editorial practices. So this filter is not likely to be effective in keeping out fake journals that are good pretenders. Scopus needs to find a way to fact-check whether the journal adheres to the declared editorial practices, including most prominently how the peer-review process is performed in practice. Unless the selection criteria are upgraded and/or the bar for inclusion is raised significantly, fake scientific journals will keep creeping in the database.” The study presented here partly confirms these conclusions since the Beall’s list inclusion was apparently right and Scopus discontinued a significant number of these titles (roughly 2/3 of the cases). Still one can also argue that ‘eventually’ the selection criteria and the bar for inclusion work and lead to the decision to discontinue a particular title and Scopus can perform proper ‘quality control’. So, we are dealing with both sides of the coin: both the Scopus and Beall’s list are not flawless and quite often both lists perform a pretty good job. Therefore both can be used as a first indication for dealing with either a good or potentially bad journal (or publisher). After that, the investigation continues...

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